

METHODOLOGICAL ASPETCS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC MECHANISM OF OF PRIVATE SCHOOLS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In world practice, targeted research has been organized to provide scientific solutions to a number of problems in the effective management of secondary educational institutions, which are considered leading participants in the private educational services market, in serving the development of the country and the prosperity of society. In this area, issues such as increasing the rating and competitiveness of secondary educational institutions, a systematic approach to building the brand of schools and managing brand capital, improving the quality of education, improving optimal management and regulation of processes, and involving mechanisms for introducing healthy competition into the educational process are being studied separately

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The concept of the organizational and economic mechanism of management of private educational institutions has a multifaceted content, it represents a harmonious system of institutional environment, organizational structure, financial and economic instruments, human capital, information and analytical systems, as well as control and incentive methods. The effective functioning of this mechanism serves to achieve the strategic goals of the educational institution, ensure competitiveness in market conditions, and continuously improve the quality of educational services. From this point of view, the process of improving the organizational and economic mechanism requires a comprehensive review of not only individual management elements, but also the entire management system.

Scientific research shows that the effectiveness of management in private educational institutions in many cases depends on how flexible and responsive their organizational structure is to market demands. Traditional hierarchical management models are not

sufficiently effective in the modern educational services market, since such models are characterized by slow decision-making, limited initiatives, and barriers to the introduction of innovations. Therefore, it is advisable to introduce matrix, process-oriented, and project-based management models in private educational institutions. Such approaches allow optimizing the distribution of responsibilities, ensuring coordination between functions, and improving the quality of management decisions.

Quality management is one of the central areas of activity of private educational institutions. In order to ensure and continuously improve the quality of educational services, it is necessary to form internal quality assurance systems, align educational programs with market requirements and increase the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market. The introduction of quality assessment indicators within the organizational and economic mechanism, the use of a results-based management model and strengthening relations with external stakeholders serve to increase the image and prestige of the educational institution.

Strategic management plays a special role in the management of private educational institutions. Being limited to short-term tactical decisions limits the institution's long-term development opportunities. Therefore, in improving the organizational and economic mechanism, it is important to clearly define strategic goals, missions and values, develop development scenarios based on an analysis of the external environment and form clear roadmaps for their implementation. This should take into account competition in the educational services market, demographic factors, technological changes and state policy.

The principles of social responsibility and sustainable development also play an important role in the activities of private educational institutions. Since the education sector directly affects the development of society, these institutions should set themselves the goal of meeting not only economic profit, but also social needs. Creating educational opportunities for the disadvantaged, developing inclusive education and strengthening cooperation with the local community increase the social effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism.

The results of the study show that a systematic and comprehensive approach to improving management efficiency in private educational institutions is of paramount importance. The organizational and economic mechanism is not just a set of separate management tools or financial instruments, but an integral system that is inextricably linked to each other, including the elements of organizational structure, strategic planning, financial management, human capital, information and communication technologies and quality management. The consistent operation of this system allows for increasing the competitiveness of an educational institution, effective use of resources, and sustainable quality of educational services.

In conclusion, it can be said that the limited capabilities of traditional hierarchical management models are not enough for modern private educational institutions. The volatility of market conditions, consumer demands, and digital transformation processes require a high level of flexibility and innovative approach from the management system. From this point of view, the introduction of process-oriented, project-based, and digital management models significantly increases the organizational efficiency of private educational institutions.

Issues of financial management and economic stability are also an important component of the organizational and economic mechanism. Diversifying sources of income, strengthening financial planning and cost control mechanisms ensure the independence and investment attractiveness of private educational institutions. At the same time, the development of human capital, improving the skills of pedagogical and managerial personnel, and the formation of a system for their effective motivation are the main guarantees of the quality of education and management effectiveness.

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